

SAGROPIA – Sustainable agriculture through novel pesticides using an integrated approach

Deliverable 6.3 Practice Abstracts – Version 1

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Contributors	<i>RTDS, Agroscope, WUR, AIT, Rovensa</i>
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1 Summary

Deliverable 6.3 of the SAGROPIA project consists of a Version 1 set of *EIP-AGRI Practice Abstracts*—concise, practice-oriented summaries designed to communicate the main results, recommendations, and practical benefits of SAGROPIA’s research on sustainable agriculture and novel, low-risk pesticides. These abstracts are tailored to be accessible and useful for farmers, advisers, and other practitioners, focusing on actionable knowledge rather than research details.

1.1 Purpose and Format of EIP-AGRI Practice Abstracts

Practice Abstracts follow the EIP-AGRI common format, a European standard for sharing agricultural innovations and results. Each abstract is a short, easy-to-understand summary (typically 1,000–1,500 characters, excluding spaces) that provides:

- The main results or outcomes of the activity (expected or final)
- Key practical recommendations and the added value for end-users
- Guidance on how practitioners can implement the results in their daily work

The abstracts avoid overly scientific language and focus on elements relevant to practitioners, such as cost, productivity, and entrepreneurial opportunities. The final versions (D6.5 – due M59) may include practical tips, photos, and examples to enhance their value.

1.2 Translation

To maximize impact and accessibility, each Practice Abstract is produced in both English and the relevant native language(s) of the project partners. This ensures that practitioners across different regions can benefit from the knowledge, regardless of their language proficiency. While English is the default for EU-wide dissemination, translated versions are essential for local uptake and are included as part of the deliverable.

1.3 Content Overview

The SAGROPIA Practice Abstracts cover IPM strategies for key crops (potato and sugar beet) across several European regions (Netherlands, Poland, Switzerland). Each abstract addresses:

- The main threats (diseases and pests) to each crop in each region
- The risk profile of current pesticides and the need for alternatives
- Results from greenhouse and field trials of SAGROPIA’s biocontrol products
- Recommendations for integrating these novel products into existing crop protection programs
- Benefits such as reduced reliance on high-risk pesticides, resistance management, and improved sustainability

1.4 Dissemination and Impact

All Practice Abstracts are publicly available and final versions (D6.5) will ultimately disseminated via the EIP-AGRI project database and other channels, supporting knowledge exchange, networking, and the adoption of innovative solutions across the EU. The abstracts are designed to be updated as new results become available, ensuring ongoing relevance throughout the project lifecycle.

2 Practice Abstracts – Template & Instructions

Short summary for practitioners in native language on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main results/outcomes of the activity (expected or final)
- The main practical recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

2.1 EPPO Maritime Zone (NL) – Potato

De teelt van aardappelen wordt bedreigd door diverse ziekten en plagen waaronder Aardappelcysteaaltjes, wortelknobbelaaltjes en plantparasitaire aaltjes, Coloradokever, Phytophthora en Alternaria. Om schade te voorkomen worden pesticiden ingezet. Een aantal daarvan zijn gekwalificeerd als “Candidates for Substitution” (CfS) waarvoor alternatieven gezocht worden. In het Sagropia project worden middelen ontwikkeld met een laag risicoprofiel. In kasproeven hebben een aantal Sagropia biologische bestrijdingsmiddelen veelbelovende resultaten laten zien. Verwacht wordt dat Sagropia middelen toegepast kunnen worden in een gewasbeschermingsstrategie als aanvulling op niet-CfS pesticiden. Voor de beheersing van aaltjes zijn beperkt middelen beschikbaar. Een grondbehandeling met een Sagropia bionematiciden kan mogelijk de populatiedichtheid van wortelknobbelaaltjes voorafgaand aan de teelt verlagen. In de aardappelteelt is Coloradokever de belangrijkste plaag. Sagropia middelen kunnen mogelijk de populatieontwikkeling reduceren waardoor schadedrempels later of zelfs niet bereikt worden. In Nederland is het advies voor de beheersing van Phytophthora mengen en afwisselen van actieve stoffen met een verschillend werkingsmechanisme. De Sagropia middelen worden ontwikkeld met een ander werkingsmechanisme dan bestaande pesticiden wat ze geschikt maakt als mengpartner en naast bestrijding van de aardappelziekte ook een bijdrage kunnen leveren aan resistentiemanagement.

2.2 EPPO Maritime Zone (NL) – Potato (English Translation)

Potato cultivation is threatened by various diseases and pests, including potato cyst nematodes, root-knot nematodes, plant-parasitic nematodes, the Colorado potato beetle, *Phytophthora*, and *Alternaria*. Pesticides are deployed to prevent damage. Several of these are classified as “Candidates for Substitution” (CfS), for which alternatives are being sought.

The Sagropia project is developing products with a low-risk profile. In greenhouse trials, a number of Sagropia biological control agents have shown promising results. It is expected that Sagropia products can be applied within a crop protection strategy to complement non-CfS pesticides.

Resources for controlling nematodes are limited. A soil treatment with a Sagropia bionematicide could potentially reduce the population density of root-knot nematodes prior to cultivation. In potato farming, the Colorado potato beetle is the primary pest. Sagropia products could potentially reduce population growth, meaning damage thresholds are reached later or not at all.

In the Netherlands, the recommendation for controlling *Phytophthora* involves mixing and rotating active substances with different modes of action. Sagropia products are being developed with a different mode of action compared to existing pesticides, making them suitable as mixing partners. Consequently, in addition to controlling the disease, they can also contribute to resistance management.

2.3 EPPO Maritime Zone (NL) – Sugar Beet

De teelt van suikerbieten wordt bedreigd door diverse ziekten en plagen waaronder bietencysteaaltjes, wortelknobbelaaltjes, laesienematoden, stengelaaltjes, bodeminsecten, virusoverdragende bladluizen en bladvlekkenziekten zoals *Cercospora*. Om schade te voorkomen worden pesticiden ingezet. Een aantal daarvan zijn gekwalificeerd als “Candidates for Substitution” (CfS) waarvoor alternatieven gezocht worden. In het Sagropia project worden middelen ontwikkeld met een laag risicoprofiel. In kasproeven hebben een aantal Sagropia biologische bestrijdingsmiddelen veelbelovende resultaten laten zien. Voor de beheersing van aaltjes zijn er geen Sagropia middelen beschikbaar, beheersing berust op monitoring van schadelijke populaties en een slimme vruchtwisseling. In de bietenteelt zijn bodeminsecten (ritnaalden) mogelijk schadelijk aan het begin van de teelt in de kiemfase. Later in de teelt worden virusoverdragende bladluizen belangrijker. Sagropia middelen kunnen mogelijk de populatieontwikkeling van insecten reduceren waardoor schadedrempels later of zelfs niet bereikt worden. In Nederland berust de bestrijding van bladvlekkenziekte voornamelijk op pesticiden met een actieve stof die als CfS is gekwalificeerd. Al vroeg in de teelt worden elicitor type middelen, die plantweerbaarheid induceren, ingezet. Toepassing van Sagropia middelen kunnen hierop mogelijk een aanvulling zijn. Dit beoogt de start van de epidemie uit te stellen. Bestrijding later in het seizoen kan gezocht worden in combinaties van niet-CfS fungiciden en Sagropia biofungiciden. Te denken valt aan tankmixen of alterneren van middelen rekening houdend met de ziektedruk en de weersomstandigheden.

2.4 EPPO Maritime Zone (NL) – Sugar Beet (English Translation)

Sugar beet cultivation is threatened by various diseases and pests, including beet cyst nematodes, root-knot nematodes, root-lesion nematodes, stem nematodes, soil insects, virus-transmitting aphids, and leaf spot diseases such as *Cercospora*. Pesticides are deployed to prevent damage. A number of these are classified as “Candidates for Substitution” (CfS), for which alternatives are being sought.

The Sagropia project is developing products with a low-risk profile. In greenhouse trials, several Sagropia biological control agents have shown promising results. For nematode control, no Sagropia products are available; control relies on monitoring harmful populations and smart crop rotation.

In sugar beet cultivation, soil insects (wireworms) can be damaging at the start of cultivation during the germination phase. Later in the season, virus-transmitting aphids become more important. Sagropia products could potentially reduce insect population development, meaning damage thresholds are reached later or not at all.

In the Netherlands, the control of leaf spot disease relies mainly on pesticides containing an active substance classified as CfS. Early in the cultivation period, elicitor-type products that induce plant resilience are currently used. The application of Sagropia products could potentially serve as a supplement to this. The aim is to delay the onset of the epidemic. Later in the season, control could be achieved through combinations of non-CfS fungicides and Sagropia biofungicides. This could involve tank mixes or alternating products, taking into account disease pressure and weather conditions.

2.5 North-East Zone (PL) – Potato

Uprawy ziemniaka w Polsce z roku na rok są coraz bardziej narażone na różnego rodzaju choroby i szkodniki. Do najgroźniejszych należą zaraza ziemniaka i alternarioza (sucha plamistość), wywoływane przez *Phytophthora infestans* i *Alternaria spp.*, a także stonka ziemniaczana (*Leptinotarsa decemlineata*), która potrafi wyrządzić poważne szkody. Dodatkowo, w bardziej suchych regionach kraju znaczące straty jakościowe w ziemniakach powodują często drutowce – larwy chrząszczy żyjące w glebie. Aby zapobiec spadkom plonów, rolnicy sięgają po środki ochrony roślin, z których część została zakwalifikowana jako tzw. „kandydaci do zastąpienia” (CfS) ze względu na potencjalne ryzyko dla zdrowia i środowiska. To z kolei skłania do poszukiwania bezpieczniejszych i bardziej przyjaznych alternatyw. W przyszłości zagrożeniem mogą stać się choroby typu stołbur (tzw. gumowatość bulw), przenoszone przez pluskwiaki z rodzajów *Hyalesthes*, *Reptalus* i *Pentastiridius*, które mogą rozprzestrzeniać się z terytorium Niemiec lub Czech. W produkcji ziemniaków dodatkowym problemem są wirusy przenoszone przez mszyce. Projekt SAGROPIA koncentruje się na opracowaniu bardziej zrównoważonych metod ochrony roślin z wykorzystaniem biopestycydów. Wstępne testy przeprowadzone w warunkach szklarniowych wykazały, że kilka biologicznych preparatów ochrony roślin opracowanych w ramach projektu SAGROPIA daje obiecujące rezultaty. Preparaty te są obecnie badane w eksperymentalnej strategii ochrony roślin (programów oprysków) i są testowane w różnych doświadczeniach polowych jako uzupełnienie tradycyjnych środków ochrony, które nie należą do grupy tzw. kandydatów do zastąpienia (Candidates for Substitution (CfS)). W przypadku chorób takich jak zaraza i alternarioza nowe produkty mogą nie tylko zastąpić substancje z listy CfS, ale także działają w inny, innowacyjny sposób, zwiększając skuteczność ochrony. Dzięki temu możliwe jest ograniczenie ryzyka powstawania odporności patogenów oraz wspieranie bardziej zrównoważonych, długofalowych strategii ochrony upraw ziemniaka w Polsce.

2.6 North-East Zone (PL) – Potato (English Translation)

Potato crops in Poland are increasingly exposed to various diseases and pests year by year. The most dangerous include late blight and Alternaria blight (dry leaf spot), caused by *Phytophthora infestans* and *Alternaria spp.*, as well as the Colorado potato beetle (*Leptinotarsa decemlineata*), which can cause serious damage. Additionally, in drier regions of the country, significant quality losses in potatoes are often caused by wireworms – beetle larvae living in the soil.

To prevent yield drops, farmers rely on plant protection products, some of which have been classified as so-called "Candidates for Substitution" (CfS) due to potential risks to health and the environment. This, in turn, prompts the search for safer and more friendly alternatives. In the future, a threat may arise from Stolbur-type diseases (known as "rubbery tubers"), transmitted by planthoppers of the *Hyalesthes*, *Reptalus*, and *Pentastiridius* genera, which may spread from the territory of Germany or the Czech Republic. In potato production, an additional problem is viruses transmitted by aphids.

The SAGROPIA project focuses on developing more sustainable plant protection methods using biopesticides. Preliminary tests conducted in greenhouse conditions have shown that several biological plant protection products developed within the SAGROPIA project yield promising results. These preparations are currently being examined in an experimental plant protection strategy (spray programs) and are being tested in various field trials as a supplement to traditional protection agents that do not belong to the CfS group.

In the case of diseases such as late blight and Alternaria blight, the new products can not only replace substances from the CfS list but also work in a different, innovative way, increasing protection efficacy. Thanks to this, it is possible to limit the risk of pathogen resistance development and support more sustainable, long-term potato crop protection strategies in Poland.

2.7 North-East Zone (PL) – Sugar Beet

W Polsce uprawa buraka cukrowego jest narażona na liczne zagrożenia ze strony szkodników, takich jak mątwik burakowy (*Heterodera schachtii*), szarek komośnik (*Bothynoderes punctiventris*), mszyce przenoszące wirusy (np. *Aphis fabae*), a także choroby liści, w tym chwościk (*Cercospora beticola*). Dodatkowym, pojawiającym się zagrożeniem jest *Pentastiridius leporinus* – wektor zespołu SBR (syndromu niskiej zawartości cukru), którego zasięg rozszerza się z Niemiec w kierunku Polski.

W ochronie roślin powszechnie stosuje się chemiczne środki ochrony, w tym insektycydy i fungicydy. Wiele z nich znajduje się na liście „Kandydatów do Zastąpienia” (CfS).

W ramach projektu SAGROPIA opracowywane są biologiczne środki ochrony roślin o niskim profilu ryzyka. Wstępne testy w warunkach szklarniowych pokazują obiecujące rezultaty w zwalczaniu wybranych gatunków owadów. W uprawie polowej produkty te mogą w przyszłości skutecznie ograniczać populacje kluczowych szkodników, takich jak szarek komośnik czy mszyce, potencjalnie opóźniając lub zapobiegając przekroczeniu progów ekonomicznej szkodliwości.

W przypadku mątwika burakowego (*Heterodera schachtii*) podstawą działań pozostaje regularny monitoring oraz dobrze zaplanowany płodozmian. Natomiast w ochronie przed chwościkiem wczesne zastosowanie preparatów typu SAGROPIA (działających jako elicytory) może pomóc opóźnić rozwój epidemii.

W dalszej części sezonu strategia ochrony może w przyszłości opierać się na łączeniu tradycyjnych fungicydów (niezaklasyfikowanych jako Kandydaci do Zastąpienia – CfS) z biologicznym produktem SAGROPIA. Stosowanie ich naprzemiennie lub łącznie (w mieszaninie zbiornikowej) może umożliwić bardziej efektywną i przyjazną środowisku ochronę roślin – dostosowaną do aktualnej presji chorób i warunków pogodowych.

2.8 North-East Zone (PL) – Sugar Beet (English Translation)

In Poland, sugar beet cultivation is exposed to numerous threats from pests such as the beet cyst nematode (*Heterodera schachtii*), the beet weevil (known locally as "szarek komośnik") (*Bothynoderes punctiventris*), aphids transmitting viruses (e.g., *Aphis fabae*), and leaf diseases, including *Cercospora* leaf spot (*Cercospora beticola*). An additional, emerging threat is *Pentastiridius leporinus* – a vector of the SBR syndrome (low sugar content syndrome), the range of which is expanding from Germany towards Poland.

Chemical plant protection products, including insecticides and fungicides, are commonly used in plant protection. Many of these are on the "Candidates for Substitution" (CfS) list.

Within the SAGROPIA project, low-risk biological plant protection products are being developed. Preliminary tests in greenhouse conditions show promising results in controlling selected insect species. In field cultivation, these products may in the future effectively limit populations of key pests, such as the beet weevil or aphids, potentially delaying or preventing the crossing of economic injury thresholds.

In the case of the beet cyst nematode (*Heterodera schachtii*), the basis of action remains regular monitoring and well-planned crop rotation. However, in protection against *Cercospora* leaf spot, the early application of SAGROPIA-type preparations (acting as elicitors) may help delay the development of the epidemic.

Later in the season, the protection strategy may in the future rely on combining traditional fungicides (not classified as Candidates for Substitution – CfS) with a biological SAGROPIA product. Using them alternately or jointly (in a tank mix) may enable more effective and environmentally friendly plant protection – adapted to the current disease pressure and weather conditions.

2.9 North-South Maritime Areas (CH) – Potato

La culture de la pomme de terre est chaque année menacée par diverses maladies et ravageurs, notamment le mildiou, les doryphores, ainsi que d'autres organismes nuisibles émergents ou réémergents. Pour protéger les cultures, les agriculteurs recourent souvent à des produits phytosanitaires, dont certains sont particulièrement préoccupants et classés comme « Candidates for Substitution » (Cfs). Des alternatives à ces produits sont donc activement recherchées. Dans le cadre du projet SAGROPIA, des produits en développement à faible risque – également autorisés en agriculture biologique – sont évalués pour leur efficacité contre les principales maladies (mildiou, alternariose) et ravageurs (doryphores). Des essais en plein champ, menés dans plusieurs régions européennes, testent des stratégies de traitement combinant les produits SAGROPIA avec des pesticides non classés Cfs. Pour certaines maladies comme le mildiou ou l'alternariose, ces alternatives sont conçues non seulement pour offrir une alternative aux « Cfs », mais visent également à introduire de nouveaux modes d'action. Cela pourrait contribuer à limiter le développement de résistances et à assurer une meilleure gestion durable des maladies à long terme.

2.10 North-South Maritime Areas (CH) – Potato (English Translation)

Potato cultivation is threatened every year by various diseases and pests, notably late blight, the Colorado potato beetle, as well as other emerging or re-emerging harmful organisms. To protect crops, farmers often resort to plant protection products, some of which are particularly concerning and classified as “Candidates for Substitution” (Cfs). Alternatives to these products are therefore being actively sought. Within the framework of the SAGROPIA project, low-risk products—which are also authorized in organic farming—that are in development are being evaluated for their efficacy against major diseases (late blight, early blight) and pests (Colorado potato beetles). Field trials, conducted in several European regions, are testing treatment strategies combining SAGROPIA products with non-Cfs pesticides. For certain diseases like late blight or early blight, these alternatives are designed not only to offer an alternative to “Cfs” products but also aim to introduce new modes of action. This could contribute to limiting the development of resistance and ensuring better sustainable disease management in the long term.

2.11 North-South Maritime Areas (CH) – Sugar Beet

En Suisse, la production de betterave sucrière a fortement diminué au cours des dix dernières années. Cette culture est notamment menacée par des maladies transmises par des insectes vecteurs, comme le syndrome des basses richesses (SBR) ou les virus de la jaunisse (« Yellow Viruses »), ainsi que par des maladies fongiques telles que la cercosporiose. Pour les maîtriser, les agriculteurs ont souvent recours à des fongicides et insecticides, dont certains sont classés comme « Candidates for Substitution » (Cfs) en raison de leur dangerosité. Des alternatives sont donc recherchées. De plus, les traitements insecticides actuels montrent une efficacité limitée contre la propagation des virus et du SBR. Le projet SAGROPIA vise à évaluer l'efficacité de produits d'origine naturelle, en cours de développement, contre les principales maladies fongiques et les pucerons vecteurs de virus, dans une approche de lutte intégrée. L'objectif est de limiter les dégâts causés par ces ravageurs sans utiliser de pesticides Cfs. Les stratégies en cours de développement dans le cadre du projet pourraient contribuer à une production de betterave sucrière plus durable en Suisse et en Europe, tout en réduisant le recours aux produits phytosanitaires les plus préoccupants.

2.12 North-South Maritime Areas (CH) – Sugar Beet (English Translation)

In Switzerland, sugar beet production has decreased significantly over the last ten years. This crop is particularly threatened by diseases transmitted by insect vectors, such as the Syndrome des Basses Richesses (SBR) or virus yellows ("Yellow Viruses"), as well as by fungal diseases such as Cercospora leaf spot. To control them, farmers often resort to fungicides and insecticides, some of which are classified as "Candidates for Substitution" (CfS) due to their hazardous nature. Alternatives are therefore being sought. Furthermore, current insecticide treatments show limited efficacy against the spread of viruses and SBR. The SAGROPIA project aims to evaluate the efficacy of natural-origin products, which are in development, against major fungal diseases and virus-vectoring aphids, within an integrated pest management approach. The goal is to limit the damage caused by these pests without using CfS pesticides. The strategies being developed within the framework of the project could contribute to more sustainable sugar beet production in Switzerland and Europe, while reducing reliance on the most concerning plant protection products.

